

RM ROADMAP

D5.2 Data Management Plan

The RM Roadmap Data Management Plan (DMP) is a document describing the different aspects related to the data collected through the RM Roadmap project.

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.2_Data Management Plan

Project full title

“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area”

Project acronym

RM Roadmap

Grant Agreement no.

101058475

D5.2: Data Management Plan

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.2_Data Management Plan

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PU – Public (fully open, automatically posted online on the Project Result platforms);

SE – Sensitive (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement);

CO – EU classified : EU restricted, EU confidential, EU secret under Decision 2015/444.

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1. Data Summary

The RM Roadmap project is committed to ensuring that its data is managed properly, shared effectively, and preserved for future use. The project's Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the key principles and practices for managing data throughout the project's lifecycle.

The DMP will be reviewed periodically, and updated to ensure that it remains relevant and effective. The review process will involve assessing the data management practices and making any necessary changes to ensure that the project's data is managed properly, shared effectively, and preserved for future use.

Each partner organisation in the RM Roadmap is responsible for complying with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) when collecting data within the WPs they participate in. The coordinating partner, EARMA, has the overarching responsibility for data management in RM Roadmap.

1.1 Purpose of data collection

Data is collected to make it possible to create an overview over training options for RMA's in Europe, and to create an evidence-based business case for effective research management. The collected data will be used in the RM Roadmap Ambassadors Network, a pan-European network of research managers that supports strategic, cross-border partnerships with industry, funding organisations, higher education, and research institutions.

1.2 Types of data collected

The data collected will concern RMs, their career paths, training, and funding opportunities available to them, etc.

- The online survey will be conducted in WP1 and WP2. The results will be retrieved in CSV format.
- The online interviews for WP1 will be recorded by Zoom in mp4 and then summarised in MSWord document.

The perceived data types are:

- project website;
- white papers;
- policy-based reports;
- training repository;
- videos.

Data formats are:

- CSV
- XLSX
- DOC

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- PDF
- HTML
- MP4

1.3 Data collection and reuse per Work Package

In this section, data collection is described for each of the project's six Work Packages (WP).

1.3.1. WP1 – Intelligence

WP1 entails an integral analysis of the career paths and working context of research managers including training, networking conditions, and future skills needs for RMs. This task will include a state-of-the-art study of career frameworks through a desk analysis, online survey, and online interviews. Going beyond previous surveys (RAAAP, RAAAP-2, and RAAAP-3, foRMAtion preparatory study), the RM Roadmap survey will cover all ERA countries and a wide group of varying types of RMs. It will identify and describe a set of at least 16 cases of institutional RM best practice and capacity adoption (8 from Widening and 8 from non-Widening countries, including centralised and decentralised university research support, but also public and private research organisations, companies, and governmental institution).

These case studies will be analysed using Qualitative Comparative Analysis, to identify success and failure factors in addition to identifying potential business cases for elaboration. The main output will be a report on an ERA-wide RM Landscape including Value Chain Mapping with the detailed analysis of case studies improving knowledge for policy-making and potentially a peer review publication improving the scientific knowledge base. A repository of the case studies and basic information is to be submitted as open data in Zenodo and OpenAIRE as well as freely accessible via the project Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP).

- Survey – we expect 2,600-2,800 responses
- Interviews – 18 online interviews, recording and transcript
- Focus groups – 4-5 focus group interviews (each with 6-8 interviewees), recording, and transcript

For the sake of comparison or reference, results of previous research will be used; primarily the RAAAP, RAAAP-2, RAAAP-3 surveys and also the preliminary study of formation (<https://www.formation-rma.eu>). In addition, certain Eurostat and OECD data will also be used.

1.3.2. WP2 – Training and development

WP2 will map and assess the current training, networking, mobility, and funding opportunities targeted to the Research Managers community, as well as contributing to the creation of an online database / dashboard of the RM ROADMAP / CARDEA projects as the single point for consultation / dissemination of such opportunities. For that, specific questions related to training, networking, mobility, and funding will be included in the RM Roadmap survey (in articulation with WP1). Detailed information on each identified opportunity will be collected through desk research and by directly contacting the organisers / training providers that will complete a short online template developed by WP2. Regarding data:

- WP2 will contribute to the survey data set (with the expected data previously mentioned in WP1)

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- WP2 will produce a training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities dataset.
 - a. Data categories: about 30 data entries (categories) will need to be collected for each type of opportunity – training, networking, mobility, and funding.
 - b. Number of entries: we expect to map at least 50 opportunities, each one of them with the 30 data entries mentioned before. The number is just an estimation, as much information regarding opportunities at national level are to be discovered.
 - c. Regarding the collection of data from the organisers/ training providers, contacts will be done mainly by e-mail (using institutional e-mail account) and organisers/ training providers will be asked to fill in data from their training opportunity in a Google forms. This will enable getting the data collected in an Excel format for further analysis.

For the sake of comparison or reference, results of previous research will be used, such RAAAP, foRMAtion, and relevant studies. The following data sets/ information was already identified:

- RAAAP: we expect to compare our RM Roadmap results with the global/ longitudinal trends we can find on RAAAP.
 1. Origin: RAAAP task force: <https://inorms.net/activities/raaap-taskforce/>
 2. The dataset for RAAAP-1 is available in Excel on Figshare:
https://figshare.com/collections/RAAAP_Research_Administration_around_the_Profession_data_sets_and_supporting_files/4022284
 3. The data set for RAAAP-2 is available in Excel on Figshare:
https://figshare.com/collections/RAAAP-2_Research_Administration_as_a_Profession_-_INORMS_follow_on_project_to_RAAAP_/4871175
 4. The data set for RAAAP-3 will also be available online, in the same format.
- HETFA Working papers: including interviews and surveys to Research Managers on training and skills:
 1. Volume 1 and 2 are available at <https://hetfa.eu/about-us/main-activities/division-for-international-cooperation/research-management-administration/>

For the sake of engagement with the RM community to participate in the analysis, WP2 will also take stock on the stakeholders mapping exercise already developed in the foRMAtion project. For that, WP2 will use the Excel documents already produced with the compilation of contacts of RM associations, networks, national and international stakeholders in HEI and at the ministry level.

1.3.3. WP3 – Roadmap and Advocacy

Data collected in WP1 will be used to create the 'business cases' containing robust analysis and justification that can be translated and utilised by the RM community within their home institutes, regions, countries and/or at the EU level. This will amplify the reach beyond the project and increase the long-term impact.

Data (names, affiliations, email addresses) will also be collected, and used in connection with the creation of RM Roadmap's Ambassadors Network.

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1.3.4. WP4 – Community, Communication and Dissemination

Will not collect data sets. Access to platform (KC) users' expertise will take place through an API connection to ORCID.

1.3.5. WP5 – Project Management

Will not collect data sets.

1.3.6. WP6 – Sustainability and Exploitation

Data sets: The main existing dataset, Subscriber CRM database, is licensed to and managed by ASTP. ASTP will be using it to reach out to our communities, in accordance with those who have given consent to receive information from ASTP. The data to be used would be the names, email addresses, institutions and host countries of individuals to be approached to participate in RM Roadmap. ASTP would extract details from Subscriber into an excel format from which to generate mailing lists for our project to then use.

KT content: aggregated data from the ASTP annual survey on KT activities is published each year via the website [KT Surveys and Metrics \(astp4kt.eu\)](https://www.astp4kt.eu) and is this in the public domain.. While raw data from individual or national surveys submitted to ASTP will not be shared in the RM Roadmap Project, ASTP may use aggregated data described in the published reports to demonstrate trends and outputs of KT activities as reported across Europe.

GDPR needs to be observed, and therefore ASTP will reach its Subscriber CRM network, only to those who are members of ASTP, or to third parties who have given consent to receive information from ASTP. Furthermore, any information that ASTP may share directly with Consortium partners to support partners Work package activities will only be those contactor details or aggregated survey data which are in the public domain.

2. FAIR data

The RM Roadmap project is committed to sharing its data openly, subject to ethical and legal considerations, adhering to the FAIR principles. The project will share data through different channels, including online data repositories, journal publications, and reports. The project will provide metadata for all data shared, including a description of the data, the format, and the conditions for reuse, as described in this section. All non-sensitive data will be made available a.o. through the project website, <https://rmroadmap.eu>.

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Project data will be described using appropriate metadata standards to ensure their discoverability and reusability.

Data collected and generated within the project will be identified by persistent file naming convention, in line with the principle:

RMroadmap- [WP number]-[date in format YYYY-MM-DD]-[activity name]-[identifier]

This principle will allow for easy consistent retrieval beyond the project lifetime. In addition, datasets will be labelled with adequate keywords for general Search Engine Optimization (SEO).

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Where relevant, CRediT (Contributor Roles Taxonomy, <https://credit.niso.org>) may be used to indicate the role and type of datasets, whenever relevant. CRediT is a high-level taxonomy, including 14 roles, that can be used to represent the roles typically played by contributors to research outputs. The roles describe each contributor's specific contribution to the scholarly output

2.2. Making data accessible

The RM Roadmap project is committed to preserving its data for future use. The project will use standard preservation techniques to ensure that the data remain accessible and usable in the long term. Digital object identifiers (DOIs) will be used to ensure that the data is easily discoverable and citable.

In addition to the project website, the RM Roadmap will use the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC, <https://eosc-portal.eu>) for publishing the data and results, making them generally accessible. Other tools like FigShare, Zenodo, OpenAIRE, internal data repositories at partners will also be used.

Data and results from RM Roadmap will be integrated into the activities of EARMA. The intent is to integrate the KCP and Ambassadors Network into EARMA's normal operations and other results from RM Roadmap may be used by EARMA, the project partners or any other stakeholders, e. g. ASTP's NAAC network or EARMA's Leiden Group members.

There is no expiration date on the data, nor on access to them. The data does not have a character that necessitates data access committees, manuals, or similar actions.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Data collected and stored in RM Roadmap uses exportable and interchangeable standard formats (text, MS Excel, etc.), not proprietary formats, see also section 1.2. The use and integration of previously established datasets, like the RAAAP surveys (see above, section 1.3), contribute to the interoperability of RM Roadmap data.

2.4. Increase data reuse

RM Roadmap data is collected with the purpose of being used to the widest possible extent, both within the project—e. g. in the RM Roadmap Ambassadors Network and the Knowledge and Community Platform (KCP— and with partners, in particular CARDEA, RM Roadmap's sister project.

Based on preliminary discussions between RM Roadmap and CARDEA project coordinators, an adjustment to the project is that RM Roadmap and CARDEA will use a common database, designed, hosted and managed by CARDEA, for data regarding training opportunities for RMA in Europe.

To the widest possible extent, all data from RM Roadmap will be in the public domain, and no need for licensing arrangements are currently foreseen.

The RM Roadmap project is designed for an impact that lasts beyond the project period.

3. Other research outputs

Detailed plans for the management and use of other research outputs from the RM Roadmap are described thoroughly in the Grant Agreement and website.

4. Allocation of resources

All costs for data management are covered in the Grant Agreement and no additional costs for making data FAIR are foreseen.

5. Data security

Each partner organisation in RM Roadmap is responsible for complying with the general data protection regulation (GDPR) when collecting data within the WPs that they participate in.

FigShare, Zenodo, OpenAIRE, internal data repositories at partners (for example, CYI KnowledgeBank (<https://repository.cyi.ac.cy/>), Crowdhelix Platform, or ASTP's CRM), may be used, as well as additional repositories if relevant.

6. Ethics

The RM Roadmap project will adhere to strict ethical standards for data management. The project will ensure that all data is collected, stored, and shared in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Ethics considerations for each of the data collection activities in the project are summarized in this list:

- Survey: Answering to the survey is voluntary and all data will be collected anonymously by setting the survey tools to not collect IP addresses. Email addresses will be only gathered from those who are interested in learning about the results and/or volunteer for interviews and/or if they agree to share more information as training providers. These data will be handled in accordance with GDPR. None of the personal data will ever be passed to third parties.
- Interviews: Participation in the interview is voluntary. The interviewees must sign a consent form before the interview. Interviewees will remain anonymous throughout data reported. None of the personal data will ever be passed to third parties.
- Focus group: Participation in the focus group is voluntary. The interviewees must sign a consent form before the interview. The responses of the participants will remain confidential, and no names will be included in any project reports. None of the personal data will ever be passed to third parties.
- Mapping exercise: training providers will be asked to complete data entries with information not available online, including the list of trainers. This participation is voluntary, and the data collection will be handled in accordance with GDPR. None of the personal data will ever be passed to third parties.
- A community of practice (CoP) will be established online, dedicated to trainers. GDPR rules and concerns will be applied to the organisation of some online meetings and possibly training events.

RM ROADMAP

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